

SELF-GLAZED CORDIERITE BODIES

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It has been found possible to prepare self-glazed cordierite bodies by incorporating suitable proportions of Gangetic silt with talcum. All the iron incidentally present as impurity is transferred to the surface layer and this produces different coloration, depending on compositions and on atmospheric condition. This segregation of iron compounds at the surface of the bodies appears to be analogous to metamorphic differentiation. A detailed study of the conditions governing this segregation has been made. *The electrical and other properties of these bodies have been found to be in close agreement with those recorded for commercial bodies.

The requisites for high frequency insulating materials are many and varied and these are not satisfied by porcelains. With a view to meeting the diverse requirements, called for by the high frequency technique, it has not even been found feasible to single out a specific composition. This is precisely the reason why a group of high frequency ceramics have been developed within recent years. The composition, specified under individual group, cannot even be claimed as an ideal one. Each such composition is but a compromise, sacrifice having to be made in some direction in order that perfection may be achieved in another.

The primary ingredient for some of the above mentioned groups is talcum and these bodies were formerly designated as "steatite bodies" or 'soap stone porcelain' (Bose, "Modern Pottery Manufacture", 1947, p. 225). At present, however, these improved bodies are preferably called after the crystals that predominate in their structure. In cordierite bodies the mineral 'cordierite', $2\text{MgO} \cdot 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{SiO}_2$, predominates and these bodies are eminently suitable for purposes where unusually low thermal coefficient of expansion, low dielectric constant and relatively low power factor are essential (Rosenthal, "Porcelain and other Ceramic Insulating Materials", 1944, Vol. I, p. 248).

The cordierite bodies are prepared from talc and China clay, the proportion of the latter may be as high as 80 to 90% (Rosenthal, *loc. cit.*). Besides small addition of alumina, fluxes and zirconium oxide are frequently made for inducing increased production of cordierite crystals.

If the surrounding atmosphere be of increasing humidity contents, the surface resistivity of a ceramic insulating material decreases. The surface resistance power of the same ware, under identical humid condition, can be increased by giving to it a coating of glaze. In addition to this, the applied glaze imparts increased tensile strength of the body (Rowland, *Electr. Eng.*, 1936, No. 55, 618). In order to improve upon the electrical and other physical properties of cordierite bodies, numerous futile attempts were made at developing a suitable glaze on them with a composition having an equally low thermal

expansion as the cordierite body. This, therefore, aroused interest to develop self-glazing cordierite bodies. A large number of experiments were made to find out a workable self-glazing composition. In all such attempts, China clay was replaced by ball clay and alumina, and incorporations of fluxes like feldspar, nepheline-syenite, zinc oxide, beryllium compounds and spodumene were aimed at. Some of these bodies were self-glazed at cone 14, but were unsuitable for mass production as the appearance of the finished articles were not very uniform (Rosenthal, *loc. cit.*). Besides, most of these bodies had too short a firing range for practical application. Although not beyond criticism, the works of Thiess (*J. Amer. Ceram. Soc.*, 1943, 26, 99) indicate a definite advance towards a satisfactory solution of this important problem.

As pointed out earlier, the alumina needed for cordierite formation is supplied in the form of clay. The plasticity of the clay also aids in the formation of bodies of complicated shapes. It was therefore considered useful to attempt at preparing a self-glazed cordierite body from talc and the plastic Gangetic silt. Rational analysis shows that this silt is a heterogeneous collection consisting of calcareous, ferruginous, siliceous and clayey materials (De, Chatterjee and Das Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc., Ind. & News Ed.*, 1948, 11, 98).

In the opinion of the present authors, the silt is considered to be an ideal substance. In the first place, it is a combination of fluxing material, colouring oxide and clay substance, and in addition, each is uniformly disseminated. Secondly, the silt softens at 1150°, and, as such, it is expected to get a fully vitrified product at a relatively low temperature. Results of experiments on Jaipur talc and silt show that it is possible to prepare self-glazed cordierite bodies with practically no porosity. The appearance of the article is also very uniform. Ordinarily, a difference of 80° to 100° between the softening and densification temperatures is considered safe for commercial production of these bodies. It has been found possible to reach the lower limit by adjusting the body compositions. Microscopic, electrical and other technical characteristics of the best samples have been studied and these are in close agreement with those recorded for good bodies.

An interesting phenomenon of concentration of almost cent per cent intrinsic iron of the raw materials on the surface was revealed, when some of the best specimens were fractured. This took place as a result of changed conditions of temperature, duration and setting of the bodies during firing. In fact, the glossiness of the body is due to the deposition of this layer. Analysis shows that the main constituents of the coloured layer are ferric oxide and magnesia and, from percentage compositions, this appears to be magnesio-ferrite, $MgO \cdot Fe_2O_3$. Leaving aside the question of chemical nature of the coloured product, it is a fact that there has been segregation of iron compounds. At the initial stage the ferric iron was uniformly distributed throughout the entire mass of the body mixture. Combination must have taken place with magnesia at the

temperature of firing and the newly formed product must have diffused through the glassy matrix.

This phenomenon appears to be analogous to metamorphic diffusion or more correctly to metamorphic differentiation. Conversely, it may be stated that a process, similar to the present one, may be operative in the production of metamorphic rocks. At elevated temperature the segregated product possesses also the peculiar property of distributing itself uniformly by migration over exposed surfaces. A detailed study of the conditions governing the segregation of iron-magnesium compound has been made, and this appears in the experimental portion.

It appears from the report of McCallier (Extract des Comptes rendus de la Société Géologique de Finlande, No. 8, 1934) that Prof. Adams did observe similar phenomenon of migration of iron. Two bricks, one of dead-burned Austrian magnesite, low in lime, and the other of synthetic clinker from dolomitic magnesite and mill scale (largely Fe_3O_4) were heated in a kiln for 60 hours. At 1450° , the brick from the synthetic clinker bent and just touched the other one. At the contact zone the iron content rose from 8.3 to 17.2%.

The expulsion of iron, in the form of compounds, from the interior to the exterior surface appears to have immense potentialities in the practical field. Production of iron-free glass is one such. Experiments are being conducted with a view to taking full advantage of this phenomenon in glass founding practice. This will, however, form the subject matter for a separate communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Table I shows the ultimate analyses of the two main ingredients used in the present investigation. For a comparative study, the average analytical figures for talc have also been included.

TABLE I

Substance.	SiO_2 .	Fe_2O_3 .	Al_2O_3 .	CaO.	MgO.	Alkalies.	Loss.
Talc	61.76%	0.10%	1.80%	2.06%	30.24%	...	4.08%
Gangetic silt	61.73	5.89	17.42	3.86	2.10	1.71%	7.27
Average values for talc (foreign)	58.88 to 61.3	0.72 to 4.65	0.07 to 2.0	0 to 1.5	29.5 to 32.3	...	

For every composition, the talc was previously calcined at a temperature of 1310° to convert it mostly into 'clinoenstatite'. This was then mixed with the

requisite quantity of Gangetic silt and the mixture was treated in a pot mill for 48 hours. Trial pieces were pressed dry, either as blocks or as small slabs. Each was allowed to dry in air for 7 days and then fired in a coal-fired muffle furnace at 1320°. The maximum temperature was raised in course of 36 hours and then allowed to soak at that temperature for 10 hours. This was followed by a slow cooling process covering 48 hours. Table II shows the composition tried, including some containing China clay and other colouring oxides, and Table III gives information about hardness, porosity, specific gravity and fired colour of the products. No such data in respect of bodies 9 to 12 appear in the table as they are not satisfactory.

TABLE II

	Sample No.											
	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.
Calcined talc (%)	89	85	80	75	70	66.5	60	55	55	55	55	55
Gangetic silt (%)	11	15	20	25	30	33.5	40	45	40	35	35	37.5
China clay (%)	5	10	8	5
MnO ₂ (%)	2	2
CoO (%)	0.5

TABLE III

Sample No.	Hardness (Moh's scale)	Porosity.	Specific gravity			Appearance.
			Apparent.	True.	Bulk.	
1	3-4	41.19	2.70	2.68	1.59	Brick red.
2	3-4	32.79	2.64	2.90	1.78	Do
3	3-4	27.88	2.50	2.82	1.90	Do
4	4-5	26.27	2.53	2.86	1.89	Do
5	5	20.93	2.47	2.71	1.81	Do
6	7	0.08	2.43	3.33	2.39	Dull deep chocolate brown.
7	7-8	0.0003	2.42	3.36	2.42	Glossy, deep yellowish brown.
8	8	Nil	2.40	3.44	2.43	Glossy, deep chocolate brown.

Compositions (1) to (3) yielded products that were in a state of incipient vitrification. With increasing clay content the progress of vitrification, too, increased and, in this respect, best results were obtained from (7) and (8). A fully vitrified body like (7) or (8) does not show any sign of crazing if it be withdrawn rapidly from a temperature of 1320° and cooled suddenly to the room temperature. Each again, developed a glossy surface that was perfectly uniform. This may be claimed to be a definite progress in the line.

With a view to ascertaining the actual densification and softening temperatures, specimens 7 and 8 were subjected to different temperatures for periods ranging between 24 and 28.5 hours. Table IV gives the results thus obtained.

TABLE IV

Temp.	Duration from start.	Density.		Porosity.	
		No. 7.	No. 8.	No. 7.	No. 8.
1180°	24 hrs.	2.61	2.71	30.1	29.01
1200°	24.5	2.80	2.88	24.2	22.26
1220°	25	2.90	2.95	20.2	18.5
1250°	26	2.96	3.06	8.9	6.6
1280°	27	2.99	3.16	0.5	0.2
1300°	27.5	3.30	3.38	0.006	0.0003
1310°	28	3.36	3.45	0.005	Nil
1330°	28.5	3.37	3.458	Nil	Nil
1360°	28	Deforms	Deforms

It is thus clear from Table IV that those bodies should be fired at 1280°—1300° in order to reduce the porosity.

Results of petrological examination reveal that each specimen (No. 7 & 8) is crystalline and finely granular. There is abundant white amorphous material in each specimen. In thin section and under high power ($\times 200$), the granular colorless mineral is observed with a medium relief. It shows occasional sector twinning. Therefore, in all probability, the colorless granular mineral observed is cordierite.

The fractured surface of each test sample has the appearance of those of normal insulator body (*vide supra*) and the glossy layer is confined only to the surface. In order to verify, if the phenomenon of concentration of iron on the surface was of accidental nature, experiments were repeated under identical conditions. The internal walls of the muffle were given a coating of white-burning China clay. The fired samples showed the same phenomenon of concentration of iron on the surface layer. This tendency towards diffusion of iron compound towards the surface is so very marked that if a fired piece be fractured and reheated at 1300°, the colorless fractured surface also becomes coated with the same glossy layer. Some portion of the deposited mass does, in fact, migrate towards the uncovered surface.

A study of the distribution of iron between the skin layer and the main bulk of the body was made. The outer layer was very carefully scraped off by means of a lathe. This was then subjected to the influence of a strong magnet for removing any extraneous iron. Similarly, some portion from the central zone of the body was also separately removed. Table V shows the percentage of iron in each portion.

TABLE V

Sample No.	% Fe ₂ O ₃ of the fired body.			Average % Fe ₂ O ₃ in the green body.
	Skin layer.	Central zone.	Average.	
7	80.32	0.71	2.26	2.52
8	80.61	0.84	2.606	2.81

It will appear from Table V that major portion of the iron is confined to the surface and the loss of iron due to volatilisation is more at the initial stage of firing. Re-firing practically does not cause further volatilisation of iron from the surface. This was tested by subjecting the fired sample again to successive heat treatment at 1300° for periods of 12 hours each. The only noticeable change was in regard to the colour of the surface layer—the reddish brown colour assumed a dark chocolate hue and the interior of the body, however, became whiter. Table VI shows the effect of further heat treatments on the fired bodies.

TABLE VI

No.	Green body.	% Fe ₂ O ₃ Twice fired			Average.	% Fe ₂ O ₃ Thrice fired	
		Average.	Skin layer.	Central zone.		Skin layer.	Central zone.
7	2.52	1.99	79.91	0.501	1.96	79.36	0.466
8	2.81	2.34	80.23	0.594	2.31	80.02	0.55

Tables V and VI show that the concentration of iron is maximum at the surface and the same is minimum near about the central zone. This suggests two-fold possibilities: Firstly, the concentration of iron should increase progressively on receding from the central zone, while the percentage of magnesia should increase in the opposite direction. Secondly, higher temperatures must favour increased diffusion of iron. For testing the validity of these deductions, samples were simply heated to different temperatures during 24 hours and the iron content of each layer was determined. Table VII embraces such results.

TABLE VII

Temp.	% Fe ₂ O ₃					
	No. 7			No. 8		
	Skin.	Central part.	Average.	Skin.	Central part.	Average.
1100°	2.34	2.301	2.313	2.61	2.63	2.618
1150°	2.32	2.30	2.301	2.606	2.61	2.606
1200°	2.306	2.304	2.30	2.59	2.57	2.59
1250°	2.29	2.28	2.28	2.52	2.505	2.503
1280°	34.70	1.08	2.28	35.40	1.42	2.492
1300°	80.5	0.602	2.23	80.1	0.59	2.48
1310°	80.8	0.60	2.20	80.78	0.56	2.46

From a reference to Table IV it is apparent that the vitrification of the bodies (No. 7 & 8) starts at 1280°; The concentration of iron on the skin layer changes suddenly at the same temperature. Vitrification therefore has perhaps something to do in this respect. In fact, white patches have been observed on the surface of fracture of samples withdrawn after shorter period of exposure at 1280°.

A study of the effect of increased duration at various temperatures on migration of iron was also made. It transpires that by prolonging the duration, no useful purpose is served unless, however, the temperature be in the vicinity of that favourable for vitrification. The results obtained have been included in Table VIII. It may be pointed out that for raising the bodies to a particular temperature, a period of 24 hours was allowed in each case and the period of soaking was varied.

TABLE VIII

Temp.	Soaking period.	%Fe ₂ O ₃ .					
		No. 7			No. 8		
		Skin.	Central part.	Average.	Skin.	Central part.	Average.
1200°	10 hrs.	2.27	2.266	2.26	2.60	2.58	2.60
	24	2.30	2.20	2.24	2.64	2.55	2.588
	36	2.60	2.02	2.216	2.78	2.32	2.49
	72	33.3	1.11	2.22	34.60	1.502	2.46
1250°	10	2.40	2.16	2.26	2.50	2.45	2.46
	24	30.26	1.16	2.24	32.20	1.53	2.43
	36	36.28	1.03	2.21	38.70	1.42	2.39
	72	80.9	0.702	2.16	80.76	0.61	2.33
1280°	10	35.2	1.06	2.37	36.6	1.46	2.41
	24	80.08	0.604	2.202	80.3	0.602	2.34
	36	80.01	0.563	2.19	80.8	0.54	2.31

Results in Table VIII confirm our previous contention in respect of the effect of temperature on the concentration of iron at the surface. Higher the temperature, the more is the rate of diffusion.

Complete analyses of the three distinct layers, viz., (a) glazed surface, (b) layer just after the glaze and (c) central zone, have been incorporated in Table IX. It may be pointed out that it was not possible to isolate the glazed layer absolutely free from the adjacent portion.

TABLE IX

No.	Portion analysed.	SiO ₂ .	Fe ₂ O ₃ .	Al ₂ O ₃ .	CaO.	MgO.
7	Glazed layer	0.54%	80.06%	0.36%	Trace	19.03%
	Layer adjacent to glaze	65.01	1.03	8.04	2.50%	23.30
	Central layer	65.2	0.63	8.06	2.48	23.61
8	Glazed layer	0.43	80.09	0.32	Trace	19.08
	Layer adjacent to glaze	66.42	1.01	8.50	2.71	22.03
	Central layer	66.50	0.61	8.42	2.66	22.41

It has not been found feasible to make a microscopic study of the glaze layer with a view to forming an idea about the precise nature of the compound formed. Results of chemical analysis, however, lend strong support in favour of magnesio-ferrite, $MgO.Fe_2O_3$, being formed.

The electrical characteristics of the bodies (7 & 8) have been included in Table X.

TABLE X

Characteristics tested.	No. 7	No. 8	Remarks.
1. (a) volume resistivity at 700° (200 volts—60 cycles).	3×10^4 ohms/cm ²	3.6×10^4 ^ (ohms percm ²)	(1) During this determination a guard ring was used to eliminate surface current, thus allowing true volume resistivity to be obtained.
(b). Do at 80°F	$> 1 \times 10^{14}$	$> 1 \times 10^{14}$	
2. Dielectric constant (at 80°F) 60 cycles/sec. 1,000 K. V./sec.	7.8 7.4	8.8 8.1	(2) Thickness of each test specimen was 1/4".
3. (a) Dielectric strength, (60 cycles, test discs 1/4" thick).	166 volts per mil.	136 volts per mil.	(3) The test discs were 3" diam. and 1/4" thick. They were immersed in oil at 80°F. Voltage at 60 cycles/sec. was increased from zero at the rate of 1.0 K.V./sec. until breakdown occurred.
(b). For test discs 6" x 6" x 1/8" thick	181 volts per mil.	151 volts per mil.	

Thus the electrical and other physical characteristics of the bodies (7 & 8) are, in general, in close agreement with those recorded by other investigators. Production of these bodies on a semi-commercial scale did not present any defect like non-uniformity of coloration.

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